

Reconstructing past land-use dynamics in Senegal

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1 Introduction

Through crops, pastures, or even wood exploitations, land-uses constitute an essential source of natural resources and ecosystem services, ranging from food, to shelter, and freshwater. Today, three-quarter of earths ice-free surfaces has been impacted by human activities [Turner et al., 2007][Kareiva et al., 2007][Winkler et al., 2021], and with the increase of the world population, the pressure on land is expected to further increase. Croplands, for example, are estimated to expand from 2.7 to 4.9 Mha each year for the next decades [Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011]. Such expansion comes at the detriment of natural land-covers through a competition for space: from 1980 to 2000, half of the expansion of agricultural lands in the tropics came at the expanse of forests, causing the loss of native habitats on which multiple species depend [Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011].

Agricultural land-uses and anthropogenic land-cover changes are responsible for a considerable amount of air, ground, and water pollution. A quarter of global GHG emissions are attributable to land-use and land-use changes, in particular through the loss of sinks for atmospheric carbon, methane emissions from livestock and rice cultivation, and nitrous oxide emissions from manure and soil fertilization s [Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011][Tubiello et al., 2015]. Land-use also accounts for more than 80% of annual water withdrawals and intensive agriculture is associated with increased soil erosion, land nutrient-loss [Bodirsky et al., 2014], and input of chemical fertilizers and pesticides into groundwater, streams, and rivers [Foley et al., 2005]. Land-uses are thus impacting the land-based ecosystem services on which they depend in a system where land is a limited resource, raising the question of the sustainability of the global food production. In this context, assessing the impact of land-uses, and causes of land-use changes allows for the study of the sustainability of land-use practices in satisfying human needs, making it a valuable tool for decision-makers.

Changes in land-uses are the result of complex human-environment interactions. Faced with such a challenge, a growing community of experts from human, environmental and geographical information sciences worked to create a body of expertise. Results include the monitoring and observation of land changes throughout the world, the identification of the mechanisms responsible and the assessment of outcomes, such as vulnerability, resilience, and sustainability, as well as associated hypothesized future evolutions of land-uses [Turner et al., 2007].

In the Sahel, interest for land change and land-use sciences has grown with increased awareness that reserves of water, arable land and vegetation are vulnerable to climate change and population pressure. Governments are faced with the challenge of sustainably satisfying the needs of one of the fastest growing population in the world, in a region characterized by economic poverty and low agricultural productivity [van Vliet et al., 2013][Oxford Analytica, 2021]. Considerable policy efforts have been undertaken in the region as a response to the severe droughts in the 1970s and 1980s. Under the impetus of several Sahelian and Sudano-Sahelian countries, the Comit permanent Inter-Etats de Lutte contre la Scheresse dans le Sahel (CILSS) was founded in 1973 for policy guidance in the field of food security and desertification reduction. Environmental policies were based on a narrative of field expansion and land degradation

41 as a result of population pressure and low rainfall. However, such narratives have proven to
42 be oversimplistic, at least in certain regions of the Sahel, leaving aside for example the eco-
43 nomic capacity of farmers to buy fertilizers [van Vliet et al., 2013]. There is thus a necessity
44 of producing more detailed scenarios of land-use change to support effective and sustainable
45 decision-making.

46 Past land-use dynamics can be assessed using high resolution satellite datasets such as Land-
47 sat [Fritz et al., 2010]. This type of analysis requires extensive study of remote sensing data. As
48 a result, up to this date, at national level in the Sahel, high confidence data is only available for
49 land uses and land-covers for 1975, 2000, and 2013, and necessitated image by image manual
50 and visual interpretation of gridded satellite data [Tappan et al., 2016]. Faced with the difficulty
51 of obtaining yearly observation data, other methods are required to assess land-use evolutions
52 in this region.

53 Modelling comes as a particularly interesting addition to land change sciences, tackling the
54 Sahelian problem of lack of data. In addition, developing a model of the human-environment
55 system allows for the testing of combined climate and policy scenarios, providing associated
56 predictions of future land-use changes. Through an observation of the expected impacts of their
57 policies, decision makers can make informed decisions for minimal environmental impacts and
58 systemic sustainability. All the more so that land-uses result from the intricate interactions be-
59 tween humans, with social and economic considerations, and the biophysical system underlying
60 the production of resources. Models allow different factors of change to be isolated to evaluate
61 their specific effects and thus point to leverages decision-makers can use for effective policies
62 [Brown et al., 2004].

63 At the global scale, multiple models were developed to reconstruct past land-use evolu-
64 tions, with limits when dealing with certain regions of the world such as Africa [Kabora et al.,
65 2024]. Methods of space allocation include analyses of statistical data such as world popu-
66 lation or interpretation of high-resolution remote sensing data when available [Ramankutty et
67 al., 2002][Klein Goldewijk et al., 2017][Winkler et al., 2021]. The Historic Land Dynamics
68 Assessment + (HILDA+) for example integrates spatially explicit land-use information and na-
69 tional scale inventories to estimate land-uses at a spatial resolution of 1 km from 1960 to 2019
70 [Winkler et al., 2021]. Larger projects such as the history database of the Global Environment
71 (HYDE) go back even further with a coverage of years 10000 BCE to 2015 CE using historical
72 population estimates and allocation algorithms [Klein Goldewijk et al., 2017].

73 On the other hand, integrated assessment models (IAMs) have been developed to predict
74 future land-use evolution. IAMs are composed of modules representing technological, environ-
75 mental and human systems, creating an integrated framework destined at modelling complex
76 human-environmental networks of interactions [Guillemot, 2022]. In the field of land change
77 science, IAMs produce quantified scenarios in response to different socio-economic and cli-
78 matic evolutions. Models responses to possible evolutions of human activities are for exam-
79 ple tested using the shared socio-economic pathways (SSPs) developed for the IPCC 5th As-
80 sessment Report [Kriegler et al., 2012]. SSPs describe plausible future societal developments

81 through changes in demographics, human development, economy, institutions, technology, and
82 environment [O'Neill et al., 2017]. In parallel, change in climate can be injected in models
83 using representative greenhouse concentration pathways (RCPs). RCPs quantify future GHG
84 emissions based on different scenarios of potential climate trajectories, depending on adopted
85 mitigation policies. Injecting SSPs and RCPs into five IAMs with land-use modules allowed
86 Schimtz et al. (2014), for example, to predict possible evolutions of pastoral lands and croplands
87 at a global scale [Schimtz et al., 2014].

88 Analyses at a global scale give very good results, however, downscaling land-use predictions
89 is a big challenge. In the Sahel, global land-use models give wrong ideas of national land-use
90 trends [Kabora et al., 2024]. For example, HILDA+, the global land-use reconstruction model
91 presented before, concluded to the stability of areas covered by crops and forests in Senegal be-
92 tween 1960 and 2019 [Winkler et al., 2021]. This result goes against the documented expansion
93 of agricultural lands and regression of forestlands [Tappan et al., 2016]. Furthermore, decision-
94 making at regional scale is essential for the implementation of policies relative to sustainable
95 development, but most data are only available at national scale like in the FAOSTAT reference
96 database [FAO, 2023].

97 In the Sahel, lack of historical data makes even national scale predictions difficult to achieve
98 due to no knowledge of past evolutions and associated mechanisms [Yang and Cui, 2019].
99 Recurrent failure of classical historical land-use reconstruction models to reproduce known
100 trends in the Sahel stems from (1) the huge gap in the scientific literature concerning land-use
101 changes in the region, the only studies available being led at the scale of villages and provinces
102 without possibility for generalization [van Vliet et al., 2013], and (2) the difficulty to distinguish
103 between actively cropped fields and fallows on remote sensing data when it comes to grass
104 fallow systems in the Sahel [Tong et al., 2020].

105 To tackle these problems, developing a model adapted to the Sahel presents itself as a very
106 needed tool to reconstruct past evolutions, and make predictions for the future. Different op-
107 tions are available, from statistical models to process-based. Statistical models assume under-
108 lying processes are stationary [Turner et al., 2007]. However, dryland systems present multiple
109 ecological and social states with functional differences depending on the systems evolution,
110 and consequently, present no equilibrium state [Reynolds et al., 2007]. As a consequence, a
111 mechanistic modelling of the system is preferable, with greater reason that it forges a better un-
112 derstanding of the effects of identified driving forces on land-use changes [Lambin and Geist,
113 2006]. A mechanistic approach also allows the model to be extended to the prediction of future
114 land-use evolutions, even in a future with unprecedented conditions. Finally, in the best case
115 scenario, this approach provides decision-makers with an analysis of mechanistic leverages
116 under their control to avoid problems such as overexploitation of lands, or conflicts between
117 land-uses.

118 Such a process-based model was proposed by Stphenne and Lambin with the dynamic
119 simulation model of land-use changes in the Sudano-Sahelian countries of Africa (SALU)
120 [Stéphenne and Lambin, 2001]. Their model is based on the global food equation, stating

121 that in a given country c , and for a given product i , the demand should be equal to the supply,
122 while taking into account imports and exports [Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011].

$$population_c \times consumption_per_capita_{c,i} = area_{c,i} \times yield_{c,i} + (imports_{c,i} - exports_{c,i}) \quad (1)$$

123 Though this study was the first to propose a complete human-environment model for the
124 Sahel, it was developed to best fit on Burkina Faso, with less in depth analysis of other Sahelian
125 countries [Stéphenne and Lambin, 2001]. In addition, the high uncertainty of parameter values
126 was not quantified. The confidence intervals on estimated land-uses thus couldn't be calculated.
127 The aim of the present study is to reconstruct land-use dynamics in Senegal with an updated
128 version of SALU.

129 Senegal is a country with good representativeness of agroclimatology in West Africa. The
130 country covers three bioclimatic zones with a pronounced rainfall gradient: Sahelian (arid) with
131 rainfall from 100 mm/year to 500 mm/year, Sudanian (semiarid) with rainfall from 500 to 1000
132 mm/year, both with a single rainy season of 3 to 4 months, and Guinean (subhumid/humid) with
133 both uni- and bimodal patterns depending on location (1000-1500 mm/year). This heterogeneity
134 in local climates, combined with social and economic differences within the population, cause
135 land-uses and land-covers to change drastically between regions [Tappan et al., 2004]. This high
136 variability poses a modelling challenge, since mechanisms impacting land-uses are very likely
137 to vary across the country. All the more so that the lack of knowledge on the Sahel implies that
138 parameter values have high uncertainty. Within the country, the Groundnut basin, a Sahelian
139 region of western Senegal, holds particular interest, with a high concentration of both national
140 population and agricultural activities [Gangneron et al., 2024]. At both national and regional
141 scale, the sustainability of land-uses represent a major concern for the population, as illustrates
142 the dependency of 60% of Senegalese on livestock [Eeswaran et al., 2022]. As in the rest of the
143 Sahel, there is thus an urgent need for studies on land-use for informed policymaking.

144 Here, we present a SALU-inspired mechanistic model destined at reconstructing historic
145 land-use evolutions. Ranges of values for parametrization are obtained from an extensive bib-
146 liographic search, and the sensitivity of outputs to these parameters is evaluated. The model is
147 then applied to predict land-use evolutions between 1961 and 2020 in Senegal, and to calculate
148 land-demands in the Groundnut basin between 1974 and 2017. At national scale, the model
149 reproduces known trends from the literature and reveals more precise characteristics of past
150 land-use dynamics along with their potential effects. On the other hand, calculation of land-
151 demands in the Groundnut basin shows the limits of the model when downscaling, requiring
152 new hypotheses to reconstruct past evolutions at such spatial scale.

153 2 Material & Methods

154 The SALU model was encoded on a Stella architecture without full transparency of calculation
155 steps [Lindfield, 1992]. Consequently, we did not replicate the model, but rather chose to

156 keep the global food equation framework, adapting ecological and economic modules to be
 157 consistent with data stemming from more recent literature (see section 9 for between-model
 158 differences). The resulting model predicts for each year the proportion of a given territory
 159 dedicated to considered land-uses based on demographic, economic, biological, and climatic
 160 data.

161 Given a set territory with available area $AREA$ in ha, this study focuses on three categories
 162 of land-uses: veg , the fuelwood extraction area corresponding to forests and woody savannahs
 163 that can be used for fuelwood extraction, $past$, the pastoral land and $crop$, the cropland. The
 164 rest of available lands, with no fuelwood resources, are considered unused and referenced as
 165 un . By assumption, these land-uses cover the entirety of available land, thus satisfying equation
 166 2 at each time step t .

$$AREA = veg(t) + past(t) + crop(t) + un(t) \quad (2)$$

167 The model is founded on the assumption used in the SALU model that production and
 168 consumption are at equilibrium when taking into account imports and exports (fig. 1). For sim-
 169 plification, each land-use is associated to the production of one specific resource: pastoral lands
 170 produce forage, croplands produce cereals and savannahs and forest lands produce fuelwood.

171 **2.1 Calculating land-demands based on consumption**

172 **2.1.1 Pastoral lands**

173 The demand for pastoral land, $past_d$, is calculated using an estimation of the forage consumed
 174 by livestock animals. The number of livestock animals, liv , is an exogenous time-series fur-
 175 ther described in section 2.3. liv is given in equivalent Tropical Livestock Unit (TLU eq.), a
 176 standardized unit taking into account the feed requirement of each species relative to that of
 177 the tropical cow taken as reference. The TLU thus provides a unified framework to analyse
 178 husbandry: while camels, cattle, and horses will have similar feeding requirements (one head
 179 corresponding to one TLU), asses, goats, and sheep have lower needs with one head corre-
 180 sponding respectively to 0.2, 0.1 and 0.1 TLU eq. [Rothman-Ostrow et al., 2020]. The quantity
 181 of forage needed for a given number of livestock can be deduced using the feeding requirements
 182 satisfied by pasture, encoded by parameter $biom_{conso}$ in tonnes/year/TLU eq. (see table 1 for
 183 parameter description). The link between production and consumption of forage is obtained
 184 through equation 3.

$$biom_{prod} \times past_d = liv \times biom_{conso} \quad (3)$$

185 On the production side, to calculate the rangeland productivity $biom_{prod}$, the relation be-
 186 tween annual precipitation and biomass production identified in [Breman and de Wit, 1983] for
 187 the Sahel is used (eq.4). Productivity is calculated as a linear function of rain, with rain an
 188 exogenous time-series described in section 2.3.

$$biom_{prod} = a_{biom_{prod}} \times rain + b_{biom_{prod}} \quad (4)$$

189 2.1.2 Croplands

190 The demand for cropland $crop_d$ (ha) is calculated under the assumption that croplands are ded-
 191 icated to cereal cultivation. Such hypothesis is justified by the dominant place of cereals in
 192 a majority of people's diet in the region [Honfoga and van den Boom, 2003]. However, the
 193 model thus excludes, due to lack of data and therefore possibility for parametrization, cash
 194 crops such as cotton and peanut, known to be cultivated in Senegal. The demand for cropland
 195 $crop_d$ (in ha/year) is calculated with the equation: $crop_d = crop_subs_d + crop_mark_d + fal_d$,
 196 with $crop_subs_d$ the lands dedicated to cereal cultivation for subsistence, $crop_mark_d$ the lands
 197 dedicated to cereal cultivation for the market, and fal_d the demand for land to leave unused
 198 for nutrient restoration. Once cultivated, cereals are either directly consumed by the rural pop-
 199 ulation or commercialized on the market to nourish the urban population. Part of the cereal
 200 consumption of the urban population also comes from imports. The urban population pop_{urb} ,
 201 rural population pop_{rur} and cereal imports cer_{imp} are exogenous time-series described in sec-
 202 tion 2.3. Using these variables allows for the derivation of $crop_subs_d$ and $crop_mark_d$, the
 203 land-demand to satisfy the subsistence needs of respectively the rural population and the urban
 204 population.

$$cer_{prod} \times crop_subs_d = pop_{rur} \times cer_{conso} \quad (5)$$

$$cer_{prod} \times crop_mark_d = pop_{urb} \times cer_{conso} - cer_{imp} \quad (6)$$

205 With cer_{conso} (in kg/inhab/year) the cereal consumption derived from literature (table 1) and
 206 cer_{prod} the cereal productivity of croplands (in kg/ha/year). cer_{prod} is an exogenous time-series
 207 described in section 2.3.

208 To allow for soil fertility restoration after cultivation, the land is periodically left unused, a
 209 phenomenon referred to as fallowing. Sub-Saharan systems are known to be low-input cropping
 210 systems [Gaiser et al., 2011] making rotation one of the main fertility-maintaining system. The
 211 demand for land lying fallow, fal_d (in ha/year), is calculated using the set ratio between the
 212 number of years under cultivation and the number of years under fallow, referred to as $cult_freq$,
 213 the cultivation frequency (see table 1 for parameter values).

$$fal_d = cult_freq \times (crop_subs_d + crop_mark_d) \quad (7)$$

214 2.1.3 Fuelwood extraction areas

215 Finally, the demand for fuelwood extraction area veg_d is calculated using equilibrium between
 216 production of wood and wood consumption of the rural and urban population (eq.8). Land wood

Figure 1: **Model presentation.** The production/consumption equilibrium hypothesis links the consumption of forage, cereals, and fuelwood to the land used for production. Provided the exogenous time-series presented in figure 2, this framework allows for an estimation of the land-use demand.

217 productivity ($fuel_wood_{prod}$ in $m^3/year/ha$) is derived from multiple literature productivity es-
 218 timations. Likewise, the bibliography provided intervals of values for $fuel_wood_{conso/rur}$, the
 219 fuelwood consumption of the rural population, and $fuel_wood_{conso/urb}$, the fuelwood consump-
 220 tion of the urban population, both in $m^3/inhab$ (see table 1).

$$fuel_wood_{prod} \times veg_d = pop_{rur} \times fuel_wood_{conso/rur} + pop_{urb} \times fuel_wood_{conso/urb} \quad (8)$$

221 2.2 Land attribution

222 Land attribution varies depending on whether land-demand can be entirely satisfied by available
 223 areas or not. If it can, land-uses are attributed to available lands without further calculations.
 224 Areas unattributed to any land-use are considered unused. In this case, increase of the demand
 225 leads to an expansion of agricultural lands at the detriment of unused areas and fuelwood extrac-
 226 tion areas. On the other hand, if the agricultural demand is too high to be satisfied by available
 227 land, the system switches towards an intensification stage, with conflicts arising between land-
 228 uses.

229 2.2.1 Expansion

230 During expansion, land-uses are first attributed to agricultural use: $past(t) = past_d$ and $crop(t) =$
 231 $crop_d$. If the surface needed for expansion of agricultural land exceeds the unused area, then
 232 deforestation and land cleaning occurs, replacing savannahs and forests ($veg(t)$) with pastoral
 233 lands and croplands. Regression of agricultural land leads to the emergence of unused areas that
 234 can not be directly used as fuelwood extraction area because of the absence of vegetation cover.
 235 After 10 years, tree regrowth leads to the conversion of said unused area $un(t)$ into fuelwood
 236 extraction area $veg(t)$ [Gaudreau and Gibson, 2015][Stéphenne and Lambin, 2001].

237 Initially, all lands unattributed to an agricultural use is categorized as fuelwood extraction
 238 area, meaning it is assumed that the land-cover produces wood resources. We assume that the
 239 part of the fuelwood extraction areas corresponding to the demand veg_d can't be deforested. The
 240 local population protects this resource for domestic consumption of fuelwood, national parks,
 241 reserves or sacred forests [Benjaminsen, 1993]. For example, some villages banned goats in
 242 favour of chickens to protect tree seedlings [Gaudreau and Gibson, 2015]. In addition, other
 243 areas are protected by their inoperability due to inaccessibility or high incidence of tsetse flies
 244 in certain regions. Efforts of the government have been made to get round this problem, with
 245 for example the 2005 tsetse eradication campaign in the Niayes and La Petite Cte aiming at
 246 the removal of African Animal Trypanosomosis [Seck et al., 2010] [Okello et al., 2022]. To
 247 take into account off-limits areas, the reduction of $veg(t)$ is inferiorly bounded by the demand,
 248 veg_d allowing for satisfaction of parts of the energetic needs. Since the protection of fuelwood
 249 extraction areas only consider the demand at the year of calculation, it doesn't guarantee the
 250 satisfaction of the demand in the next years if the demand increases. In this case, the population
 251 is hypothesized to compensate using other sources of energy.

Parameter	Description	Unit	Value in SALU	Literature range	Sources	Conditions
<i>biom_{conso/expansive}</i>	Livestock forage consumption under expansive agriculture	tonnes/eq. TLU/year	4.6	[3.4, 6.1]	1: Le Hourou and Hoste (1977) 2: Behnke and Scoones (1993) 3: Leeuw and Tothill (1990)	1: African Sahelo-Sudanian zone, 1977 2: African savannahs, 1983 3: Sub-Saharan Africa, 1993
<i>biom_{conso/intensive}</i>	Livestock forage consumption under intensive agriculture	tonnes/eq. TLU/year	2.3	[1.7, 3.0]	1: Le Hourou and Hoste (1977) 2: Behnke and Scoones, (1993) 3: Leeuw and Tothill (1990)	1: African Sahelo-Sudanian zone, 1977 2: African savannahs, 1983 3: Sub-Saharan Africa, 1993
<i>cer_{conso}</i>	Consumption of cereals of the Senegalese population	kg/inhab/year	360	[109.8, 327.1]	1: Bricas et al. (2013) 2: FAOSTAT analytical brief (2023) 3: Honfoga and van den Boom (2003) 4: Lipinski et al. (2013) 5: FoodData Central (2019)	1: Mean on Abidjan, Bamako, Bissau, Cotonou, Dakar, Lom, Niamey and Ouagadougou, 2008. 2: Africa, 2010 - 2021 3: Sahelian countries, 1961 - 2000 4: Global, 2011 5: Global, 2019
<i>cult_freq</i>	Cultivation frequency driving the crop-fallow cycle	year	2	[1, 3]	Bonetti and Jouve (1999)	Sub-Saharan Africa, 1999
<i>fuel_wood_{conso/rur}</i>	Fuel wood needs : rural consumption	m ³ /inhab/year	0.65	[0.41, 1.26]	Ki-Zerbo (1981)	Senegal, 1981
<i>fuel_wood_{conso/urb}</i>	Fuel wood needs : urban consumption	m ³ /inhab/year	0.85	[0.41, 1.26]	Ki-Zerbo (1981)	Senegal, 1981
<i>fuel_wood_{prod}</i>	Fuelwood productivity of natural vegetation	m ³ /year/ha	0.75	[0.1, 3.0]	Picard et al. (2006)	Dry savannahs in Africa
<i>a_{biom_prod}</i>	Slope of <i>biom_{prod}</i>	Tonnes/ha/m	0.00375	[0.0025, 0.005]	Breman and De Wit (1983)	Central Mali, 1976 - 1981
<i>b_{biom_prod}</i>	Intercept of <i>biom_{prod}</i>	Tonnes/ha	0.15	[-0.20, 0.30]	Breman and De Wit (1983)	Central Mali, 1976 - 1981
<i>crop_past_ratio</i>	Crop/pasture trade-off coefficient	None	0.4	[0, 1]		

Table 1: **Available data on model parameters.** Presentation of model parameters model along with available data derived from literature. The *Value in SALU* column presents the values used in [Stphenne and Lambin, 2001].

2.2.2 Intensification

If deforestation is not enough to support agricultural expansion, meaning $AREA - past_d - crop_d < veg_d$, then the system switches towards intensification. To satisfy the food demand, different intensification strategies are put in place in parallel by the population: yield increases through the addition of fertilizers and a higher number of working hours, a decrease in pastoral lands and reduced fallows. The model takes into account all three strategies.

First, the increase in yield is considered through the exogenous time-series for cereal productivity *cer_{prod}*. Second, the demand for pastoral lands is decreased through a switch in the livestock consumption patterns: during expansion, only 1/3 of livestock’s biomass consumption comes from crop residues. Under intensification, the consumption of crop residue can rise up to 2/3, reducing the need for land and leaving space for cultivated fields. This switch in consumption patterns is encoded in the model with the parameter *biom_{conso}* taking the value *biom_{conso/expansive}* when agriculture is expansive, and *biom_{conso/intensive}* during intensification (table 1). Such strategy is not sufficient to withstand high demands for forage and would thus lead to livestock losses if fodder is not imported. These losses wouldn’t necessarily appear on the figure 2 time-series, since the stocks could be renewed from one year to the next. Since imported fodder wasn’t considered in the model, livestock losses were not estimated. Finally, the

269 tradeoff between reduction of pastoral lands and reduction of fallows is encoded with equation
 270 9 in which we introduce $crop_past_ratio$, a dimensionless coefficient of priority for croplands
 271 over pastoral lands.

$$fal(t) = fal_d - (crop_d - crop(t-1) + past_d - past(t-1) - un(t)) \times (1 - crop_past_ratio) \quad (9)$$

272 Higher pressure for land translates in higher $crop_d$ and $past_d$ values and consequently, lower
 273 $fal(t)$. The fallowing time thus decreases to leave space for pastoral lands. The lands attributed
 274 to active cultivation are hypothesized not to be affected by the conflicts between land-uses.
 275 Reduction of fallowing time continues, with increasing crop and pastoral demands, until no
 276 lands are left unused for nutrient restoration ($fal(t) = 0$).

277 **2.3 Exogenous variables**

278 Each application of the model requires parameter values for the ten parameters of table 1
 279 and time-series for each of the six exogenous variables displayed in black in figure 1. A
 280 bibliographic search on the Sahel revealed heterogeneity and sparsity of available data for
 281 parametrization. Despite this limitation, analysis of the literature allowed us to gather the
 282 information presented in table 1, and in particular ranges of values for each parameter. Two
 283 scales were considered for analysis: national, on the entirety of the Senegal territory, and on
 284 the Groundnut basin, defined here as the combination of administrative regions Diourbel, Fat-
 285 ick, Kaffrine, Kaolack and Thies. Although this zone heavily relies on agriculture, with 60%
 286 of Senegalese farms concentrated in the area, little is known on the quantitative evolution of
 287 land-uses [Bourgoin et al., 2023][Gangneron et al., 2024]. Downscaling the model could thus
 288 provide valuable information. We used the geographic divisions described by the global admin-
 289 istrative areas (GADM) database [Hijmans, 2022]. Data availability conditioned the analysis to
 290 cover the period 1961 to 2020 at national scale, and 1974 to 2017 at regional scale. Exogenous
 291 variables are presented in figure 2.

292 **2.3.1 National scale**

293 The time-series used as exogenous variables at national scale mostly come from the Food and
 294 Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAOSTAT) database [FAO, 2024]. The dataset
 295 provides us with the rural and urban population (pop_{rur} and pop_{urb}), as well as the mean na-
 296 tional cereal yield (cer_{prod}), the livestock (liv), and cereal imports (cer_{imp}). The cereal yield
 297 accounts for fonio, maize, millet, rice and sorghum. Livestock is obtained using the number of
 298 animals for species asses, camels, cattle, goats, horses, or sheep. Finally, the net cereal imports
 299 are estimated by subtracting imports from exports using categories Cereals and Cereal prepara-
 300 tions defined by the Central Product Classification (CPC) [United Nations, Statistics Division,
 301 2015].

Figure 2: **Exogenous variables for Senegal and the Groundnut basin.** Blue corresponds to national scale, red to the Groundnut basin. Data is presented per unit space for between-scale comparability. The national rangeland productivity values are calculated over 1000 randomly drawn parameter sets using equation 4. For cereal imports, the same time-series is used for national and regional scale. Sources are the following: at national scale, the FAO for population densities, the livestock density, the crop yield, and cereals imports [FAO, 2024]; ERA5 for rain data [Hersbach et al., 2020]. At regional scale, the ANSD for population densities [ANSD, 2006][ANSD, 2016][ANSD, 2023]; the GLW database for the livestock density [Gilbert et al., 2018]; the STICS model for the crop yield [Brisson et al., 1998]; the STEP model for the rangeland productivity [Mougin et al., 1995]; the ANACIM for rain data [ANACIM, 2017].

302 We chose to use the rain time series provided by ERA5 [Hersbach et al., 2020]. Although
303 ERA5 data can present seasonal deviations from observations, in particular in July due to the
304 difficulty to model mesoscale convective systems in western Africa [Lavers et al., 2022], it is a
305 reference weather model for the past decades. Data is available at a 31 km scale. We used the
306 mean ERA5 values across Senegal territory (fig. S1). The rangeland productivity ($biom_{prod}$)
307 could then be estimated using equation 4.

308 2.3.2 Regional scale

309 At the scale of the Groundnut Basin, the ANSD, the Senegalese statistics and demography
310 agency, provides rural and urban survey data for years 1976, 1988, 2002, and 2013 to 2017
311 [ANSD, 2006][ANSD, 2016][ANSD, 2023]. Missing data is estimated using splines. We hy-
312 pothesize that the cereal imports per urban inhabitants was the same at national and regional
313 scale. That is to say that $cer_{imp/reg} = cer_{imp/nat} \times pop_{urb/reg}/pop_{urb/nat}$.

314 Regional livestock values are extracted from the Gridded Livestock of the World (GLW)
315 database for years 2009 and 2015 [Gilbert et al., 2018]. The GLW database comes as a re-
316 sponse to the scarcity of subnational livestock data through the use of a per-pixel attribution
317 model. Statistical inferences are made based on environmental predictor variables to estimate
318 how livestock distributes within census units, such as countries. Species considered were cat-
319 tle, goats, horses, and sheep, with a spatial resolution of approximately 10 km. The average
320 proportion of national livestock situated in the Groundnut basin is calculated using GLW data
321 and national livestock values for the corresponding years. This proportion is hypothesized to be
322 constant. As a result, for each year, approximately 38% of national livestock is attributed to the
323 Groundnut basin.

324 Rain time-series (fig. S1) are obtained by averaging ANACIM weather station data over
325 Dakar, Diourbel, Kaolack, and Kongheul [ANACIM, 2017]. We only have access to months
326 May to November, with low impact on yearly values since rainfall is rare December to April,
327 the wet season only beginning in May [Fall et al., 2006].

328 The cereal yield (cer_{prod}) is estimated using the multidisciplinary simulator for standard
329 crops model (STICS) [Brisson et al., 1998] using ANACIM rain data as input. The soil com-
330 position is estimated through field work on a representative site of the region's soil (Bambey),
331 with approximately 5% of clay. Calculations are made for millet using the STICS calibration
332 provided by Sow et al. (2024) [Sow et al., 2024]. Additionally, having the Groundnut basin's
333 soil composition allows us to use a model of the seasonal herbaceous layer in the Sahel known
334 as STEP [Mougin et al., 1995] to estimate the rangeland productivity ($biom_{prod}$), instead of
335 equation 4. Using this model isn't possible at national scale because of the presence of multi-
336 ple bioclimatic zones, STEP being only adapted to Sahelian conditions. STEP was proven to
337 simulate the Sahelian herbaceous growth with high reliability at both local and regional scale
338 [Pierre et al., 2015]. The possibility to use the model here thus allows us to obtain more de-
339 dependable results at regional scale. Simulated biomass productivities highlight that equation 4
340 tends to overestimate the rangeland biomass productivity (fig 2). This overestimation cannot be

341 explained by lower rainfall values in the Groundnut basin, since it rains more in mean regionally
342 than nationally (fig. S1).

343 **2.4 Analysis outline**

344 Before applying the model, a sensitivity analysis is carried out. The 10 parameters have high
345 value uncertainty (table 1). Each one thus contributes to the output variance. To quantify this
346 effect and identify ways to find more precise results, the role of parametrization is investigated.
347 With the possibility to rank parameters according to their relative significance, a sensitivity anal-
348 ysis is carried out to investigate the impact of each model parameter uncertainty on the model
349 outputs. The goal is to identify parameters with low effect, and establish which parameters to
350 investigate to decrease model output variance in future studies using this model.

351 We decided to use the δ -sensitivity measure developed by Borgonovo [Borgonovo, 2007].
352 This density-based sensitivity analysis method quantifies the normalized expected shift in the
353 distribution of an output provoked by one parameter over all its possible values. δ -indices range
354 from 0 to 1, with 0 corresponding to an output independent of the parameter at hand and 1 to
355 a case where the parameter entirely determines the output. Higher values thus correspond to a
356 higher effect. This method was chosen due to its minimum computational cost, its consideration
357 of the entire distribution of inputs and outputs, and its accounting of parameter correlations.
358 10000 samples of parameter sets are generated, and associated model outputs are calculated
359 using national exogenous time-series. Then for each output land-use, δ -indices are computed
360 using the SCALib module [Cassiers and Bronchain, 2023]. Results are discussed in section 3.1.

361 Subsequently, 1000 parameter sets are sampled for application of the model to land-use pre-
362 diction. First at the national scale, with exogenous time-series of section 2.3.1, then at the scale
363 of the Groundnut basin with section 2.3.2 data. The Python language is used for the entirety
364 of our study. Modules NumPy and Pandas are used for computation, and data manipulation
365 [Harris et al., 2020][McKinney, 2010]. Both the sensitivity analysis and the model application
366 require exploring of the parameter space through rigorous sampling. The SciPy python mod-
367 ule [Virtanen et al., 2020] is used for this purpose, with a uniform probability distribution on
368 parameter intervals. The code is made fully accessible [Dupré, 2024].

369 **3 Results**

370 **3.1 Parameter sensitivity**

371 δ -indices are presented in figure 3. *crop_past_ratio*, *biom_{conso/expansive}* and *biom_{conso/intensive}*
372 are parameters that only intervene during either expansion and intensification, contrary to other
373 parameters that are used at each step regardless of the intensification status. Their global ef-
374 fect on the model output is thus expected to be impacted by the number of years spent in
375 agricultural expansion or intensification. On the other hand, the difference in effect between
376 *fuel_wood_{conso/rur}* and *fuel_wood_{conso/urb}* could be explained by the consistently higher pro-

Figure 3: **Differences in model parameter sensitivity.** Delta indices are calculated over model outputs for 10000 randomly sampled parameter sets drawn from intervals in table 1 National exogenous variables are used for the simulations. All indices have confidence intervals below 0.006.

377 portion of the population living in rural areas (fig.2), making $fuel_wood_{conso/rur}$ a more influ-
 378 ential parameter.

379 With a very low mean delta index of 0.039, $crop_past_ratio$, the crop/past priority ratio, is
 380 the least influential parameter (fig.3). No information was known on this parameter, and refining
 381 this parameters interval of values would require extensive analysis of the conflicts between
 382 land-uses. Consequently, the low effect of this parameter’s uncertainty on the model output will
 383 facilitate the work of reducing model output uncertainty in future studies.

384 The cereal consumption, cer_{conso} , stands out with a very high effect on model outputs and
 385 in particular on $crop_mark$ and $crop_subs$. Delta indices being lower than 0.05 for the other
 386 parameters when considering $crop_mark$ and $crop_subs$, cer_{conso} is even the only influent pa-
 387 rameter for these outputs. The uncertainty on cer_{conso} thus highly affects the land-use recon-
 388 struction, indicating that investigating this parameter should be prioritized when looking to
 389 reduce model output uncertainty. At a lower level, $fuel_wood_{prod}$, a_{biom_prod} , $cult_freq$, and
 390 $biom_{conso/expansive}$ also have significant effects, distributed over multiple outputs. Investigating
 391 these parameters could thus also help reduce model output uncertainty.

392 3.2 National scale

393 3.2.1 Land-use evolutions

394 Starting at the national scale for which the model was designed, results are presented in figure 4
 395 with panel b presenting the median land-use values across all simulations. The stacked medians
 396 (fig. 4b) don’t amount to the available area represented as a dotted line because median values

Figure 4: **National land-use evolution.** (a) **Model outputs.** Box plots of simulation outputs for 1000 randomly sampled parameter sets drawn from intervals in table 1. Output classes are *fal* (fallow), *crop_subs* (croplands satisfying subsistence needs), *crop_mark* (croplands cultivated for the market), *un* (unused areas), *past* (pastoral lands), and *veg* (fuelwood extraction areas). Results are displayed as the fraction of national territory occupied by each land-use. Boxes represent the first and third quartiles of data. Whiskers indicate the first quartile minus 1.5 times the interquartile range, and the third quartile plus 1.5 times the interquartile range. Medians are indicated in red. (b) **Trend overview.** Evolution of land-use occupation at national scale (medians). For comparison, Tappan et al. (2016) data are added as bar plots for years 1975, 2000, and 2013 [Tappan et al., 2016]. The dotted line indicates the available national surface.

397 for each land-use are not necessarily from the same simulation, where equation 2 applies. Model
398 outputs present a very high variability, as illustrate fuelwood extraction areas (*veg*) with values
399 ranging from 0% to 69% of covered territory from 1968 to 1991 (fig. 4a). However, land-use
400 evolution trends can be identified through the general dynamics across simulations.

401 Initially, fuelwood extraction areas (*veg*) cover more than half of national territory, whereas
402 in 2020, that proportion gravitates around 25% of occupied territory (fig. 4a). Due to the pres-
403 sure from other land-use categories to satisfy the needs of the growing population, fuelwood
404 extraction areas decreased quickly to their minimum values between the 1960s and the 1970s.
405 The demand for agricultural land thus led to deforestation. However, unused areas were still
406 present until the end of the 1980s, indicating that the demand did not continuously exceed
407 available space during this period. No land was left unused for long enough to allow for refor-
408 estation. The evolution of *veg* and *un* is a good proxy of the state of the system: between the
409 1960s and the 1970s, the system was under expansion, then between the 1970s and the mid-
410 1990s intermittent intensification years led to the emergence of unused areas that disappear with
411 the mid-1990s switch to continuous intensification with median values never leaving zero for
412 *un* (fig. 4a).

413 Due to the strong Senegalese demographic increase (fig.2) and the model hypotheses, the
414 amount of land dedicated to *crop_mark* and *crop_subs* increased to satisfy the higher consump-
415 tion needs of both the rural and urban population. However, this increase stops in the 2000s to
416 leave in place a plateau and even a decrease after the 2010s. This phenomenon is the result of
417 the high increase in cereal yield observed on FAO data, with values doubling between the 2000s
418 and the 2020s (fig.2). The necessary quantity of lands for equal production thus significantly
419 decreased.

420 In the case of fallows, allocated lands slightly increase until 1998. Consecutively, the 2000s
421 show a decline in fallows, with medians diminishing of one third. In addition, a considerable
422 number of simulations predict a collapse of fallow lands, with the lower quartile approximating
423 zero from 2004 to 2020. Since *crop_mark* and *crop_subs* strongly increased from the 1960s
424 to the 2000s, the low increase of fallowing land *fal* indicated that the crop-fallow cycle was
425 already impacted by pressure for land before the collapse in fallow lands. This phenomenon
426 will be further explored in section 3.2.2.

427 Finally, pastoral lands switch from covering less than 25% of national territory in 1961
428 to covering half available lands in 2020. Pastoral lands increased until the 1970s, plateaued
429 until the mid-1980s, before continuously increasing until the end of the simulation time. This
430 evolution is coherent with the evolution of livestock (fig.2). Livestock increased, until the severe
431 1970s and 1980s droughts caused high mortality and thus a plateau and slight decrease of animal
432 populations. Then, starting in the mid-1980s, livestock continuously increased. In addition, the
433 decrease in cultivated lands as a result of the increased cereal yield left enough space for pastoral
434 land to expand even in the state of continuous territory saturation starting in the 1990s.

435 To evaluate the credibility of the predicted land-use evolutions, we compared model outputs
436 to independent data from [Tappan et al., 2016]. This study is based on an image-by-image

Figure 5: **National land-use effects.** The 1000 simulations ran at national scale are analysed through three intensification proxies: the (a) **saturation frequency** meaning the fraction of simulations with no space left for agricultural expansion at each year, the (b) **cultivation frequency** corresponding to the ratio between fal and $crop_{mark} + crop_{subs}$, and the (c) **percentage of livestock feeding requirements satisfied by pastures.** The latter is obtained by dividing the produced forage $past(t) \times biom_{prod}(t)$ by the total consumption needs $\frac{3}{2} \times biom_{conso/expansive} \times liv(t)$ Panels b and c display results as box plots with darker points indicating medians.

437 photo interpretation of satellite data for 1975, 2000 and 2013 at a 2 km spatial resolution. They
 438 worked with a mix of land-use and land-cover classes, with no exact correspondence with the
 439 type of output we study. Their cultivated areas and fallows class (4b) corresponds, in the model,
 440 to the sum of $crop_{subs}$, $crop_{mark}$ and fal . Forests, steppes, and savannas, on the other hand,
 441 can correspond to either un , $past$, or veg depending on the attributed land-use and should thus be
 442 considered as an upper bound for the sum of these three outputs. Comparison between the three
 443 data points and the median outputs shows the correct orders of magnitude of model predictions,
 444 with a tendency of cropland values to be overestimated by the model. Considering the lack
 445 of data on both parameter values and expected land-use values, such results were considered
 446 sufficiently satisfactory given the current state of knowledge.

447 3.2.2 Land-use effects

448 To further analyse the implications of predicted outputs, we studied intensification proxies used
 449 as indicators of land-use impacts. Looking at the yearly proportion of simulations in intensi-
 450 fication mode (fig. 5a) confirmed the gradual switch to intensification observed in figure 4a:
 451 the agricultural system is under continuous expansion until the 1970s. Consecutively, peaks
 452 of territory saturation start occurring, with agricultural expansion still holding a predominant

453 place. The probability of the intensification state gradually increases until all simulations pre-
454 dict territory saturation starting in the mid-1990.

455 Looking at the cultivation frequency, that is to say the number of years cultivated lands are
456 left fallow, more than 75% of simulations predict values between one and three years until the
457 mid-1990s (fig. 5b). Surprisingly, a significant proportion of simulations predicts cultivation
458 frequencies under 1 year even in the beginning of the studied period before the switch towards
459 intensification. A decrease is observed starting in the mid-1990s. Subsequently, from the 2000s,
460 75% of simulations predict cfs under two years, and 25%, approximately 0 year. There is thus
461 a high probability that the territory saturation had a strong negative impact on the cultivation
462 frequency, particularly from the beginning of the 2000s.

463 Livestock are also impacted by territory saturation (fig. 5c). In 1972, 1978, and the mid-
464 1980s, half of simulations predict a quantity of pastoral lands insufficient to satisfy the two
465 thirds of livestock consumption. Until the 1990s, crop residues must have thus been used occa-
466 sionally as a substitute for the missing forage. Starting from the 1990s, the forage consumption
467 needs of livestock are continuously unmet by available pastoral lands. A significant proportion
468 of simulations even predict a satisfied consumption below $\frac{1}{3}$ of consumption needs, meaning
469 without an economic capacity to compensate using fodder, livestock losses are likely to have
470 occurred.

471 **3.3 The Groundnut basin's land-use demands**

472 Having applied the model at national scale, we downscaled the analysis to the Groundnut basin.
473 The 1000 previously sampled parameter sets were used, in addition to the regional exogenous
474 time-series (fig. 2). The corresponding land-use demands are presented in figure 6. In 1974,
475 the demand for agricultural lands, excluding fallows, already amounts in median to the en-
476 tirety of the region's surface (fig. 6b). In parallel, the hypothesis of fuelwood extraction area
477 preservation would require 10 to 60 % of that surface to be attributed to *veg*, as predict 75%
478 of simulations (fig. 6a). All land-demands increase with time during the period of analysis
479 (fig. 6a). Notably, the 1991 and 2014 drops in yield (fig. 2) cause peaks in *crop_subs* and
480 *crop_mark* demands (fig. 6a). Consequently, while the global increase in demand causes the
481 cumulated median demand to reach twice the available territory, years 1991 and 2014 show
482 peaks at more than thrice (fig. 6b). This land-demand calculation shows the impossibility to
483 satisfy consumption demands using only the Groundnut basin's available territory, even when
484 considering known intensification strategies. Such a high demand renders obsolete our land-
485 attribution framework, since resources from outside the Groundnut basin need to be imported
486 to satisfy the demand.

487 Tappan et al. (2016) data show that the Groundnut basin is a primarily agricultural region
488 with approximately 60% of the territory covered by cultivated lands and fallows (fig. 6b),
489 whereas croplands only cover approximately 17% of the national area (fig. 4b). Forests, steppes,
490 and savannas declined from 37% in 1974 to 28% in 2013 (fig. 6b), coverages far from the 80
491 % of territory covered by this class nationally (fig. 4b). Comparing national and regional

Figure 6: **Land-demand evolution in the Groundnut basin.** (a) **Model predictions** for $past_d$ (the demand for pastoral lands), $crop_subs_d$ (the demand for croplands for the rural subsistence needs), $crop_subs_d$ (the demand for croplands for the market), and veg_d (the demand for fuelwood extraction areas). $past_d$ is calculated under the hypothesis of minimal livestock consumption (with $\frac{2}{3}$ of consumption needs satisfied by crop residues). Box plots of simulation outputs are displayed for 1000 randomly sampled parameter sets drawn from intervals in table 1. Results are displayed as the ratio between land-demand and available territory. Medians are plotted in red. (b) **Trend overview.** Median evolution of land-demands. For comparison, Tappan et al. (2016) data are added as bar plots for years 1975, 2000, and 2013 [Tappan et al., 2016]. The dotted line corresponds to the Groundnut basin surface.

492 exogenous time-series provides insights into the exploding land-demands of the Groundnut
493 basin. To begin with, the demographic pressure is very high regionally. The rural density in
494 particular is consistently approximately three times higher in the Groundnut basin relative to
495 nationally, explaining the high *crop_subs_d* values in figure 6b. In addition, 38% of national
496 livestock is hypothesized to be situated in the Groundnut basin, whereas the Groundnut basin
497 only represents 18% of the national surface. As a result, the livestock density is approximately
498 two times higher regionally (fig. 2).

499 Tappan et al. (2016) data and the exogenous time-series paint the picture of a highly popu-
500 lated region, where lands are primarily attributed to agricultural use. However, considering the
501 magnitude of land-demands, the precise yearly evolution of land-uses could not be estimated
502 using this model.

503 **4 Discussion**

504 The present study aimed at developing and applying a land-use reconstruction model to Senegal.
505 Data availability conditioned the analysis to the period between 1961 and 2020 at national level,
506 and between 1974 and 2017 in the Groundnut basin. At national level, the model predictions
507 were validated by available literature. In the Groundnut basin, however, the model couldnt be
508 applied due to demands far exceeding available space, requiring additional hypotheses to model
509 regional dynamics.

510 At national scale, the decrease in fallow, associated with the switch to intensification, re-
511 produce literature trends. A decline in fallowing times was observed between the 1960s and
512 the 1980s [Bonetti and Jouve, 1999][Masse et al., 2018]. In addition, the models prediction
513 of shorter crop fallow cycles echoes the multiple field studies showing a declining fertility of
514 arable lands as a result of fallow disappearance, and insufficient fertilizer to compensate [Niane-
515 Badiane and Szempruch, 1998][Gangneron et al., 2024]. In addition to the correct prediction
516 of the disappearance of fallows, results are coherent with the 40% decrease in vegetated lands
517 between 1960 and 2015 observed in [Gaudreau and Gibson, 2015], and with the 26% increase
518 in cultivated lands observed in [Tappan et al., 2016] between 1975 and 2013. The model results
519 are thus consistent with known land-use evolution trends.

520 It is not known since when intensification strategies have been implemented in Senegal, nor
521 the extent of such intensification. The only studies available are at local level, or focus on inten-
522 sification as an agricultural innovation and not the result of land saturation [Sall, 1992][Santiago
523 et al., 2023]. When applying SALU to Senegal, Lambin (2001) predicted a switch to continuous
524 intensification starting from 1976, but no uncertainty was taken into account [Lambin, 2001].
525 Through the national scale assessment of land-use saturation, we predicted the probable emer-
526 gence of intensification years in the 1970s before a switch to continuous intensification in the
527 mid-1990s. Predictions thus do not contradict Lambin's results, but rather refine them through
528 the consideration of parameter ranges.

529 Downscaling the model to the Groundnut basin wasnt possible using the same framework

530 because of the very high consumption demands considering the size of the territory. The hypoth-
531 esis according to which the demand of the population is satisfied by the local production is thus
532 false at this scale. The qualitatively assessed demographic pressure on lands and resources have
533 concerned the public authorities as soon as the 1930s. Despite measures to relocate populations
534 to available arable lands, both colonial authorities and, after the independence, the Senegal gov-
535 ernment, failed at decongesting the region and hindering the demographic increase. The high
536 agricultural land-demands found in this study corroborate the pressure for resources in this re-
537 gion. Now, although studies predicted as soon as the 1980s a deterioration in the agricultural
538 system and the appearance of serious symptoms of overcrowding [Lericollais, 1983], agricul-
539 ture remains economically viable in the region, and no exodus movement were recorded [Lalou
540 and Delaunay, 2015]. The population managed the demographic pressure through temporary
541 work migrations to the city. The rural population is not self-reliant for the production of the
542 cereals needed for their consumption. Through mutual aid networks, workers provide the share
543 of cereals lacking and act as buffer in the event of production downturns. The parallel decline
544 in appeal of the traditional agricultural work for younger family members contributed in a turn
545 to non-farming economic activities, locally or through migration, for an economic and social
546 emancipation [Lalou and Delaunay, 2015][Gangneron et al., 2024]. With this diversification in
547 economic activities, families became less dependent on agriculture for their needs.

548 This change in economic activities led to a lower demand for lands to satisfy consumption
549 needs. In addition, agriculture in this region is organized around two crops: millet, mainly
550 cultivated to satisfy subsistence needs and thus accounted in the model, and groundnuts, a cash
551 crop historically established through colonial influences [Gangneron et al., 2024]. Most Sene-
552 galese groundnut growing areas are located in the Groundnut basin and the crops are mainly
553 destined for exports and thus provide an income for the rural population to satisfy their con-
554 sumption needs [Georges et al., 2016]. Without a specific economic module in the model, this
555 phenomenon is not taken into account. Furthermore, though the production of groundnut tends
556 to decrease, agriculture has seen a rise in its monetization. Watermelon cultures, and market
557 gardening, for example, are increasingly implemented, and the money generated is used to buy
558 rice, school supplies or other essential items [Gangneron et al., 2024]. Our inability to apply the
559 model regionally could thus be the result of an overestimation of the part played by subsistence
560 crops in the rural inhabitants' consumption.

561 Faced with a demand exceeding the limits of natural resources, the Groundnut basin pop-
562 ulation adapts, pointing out that our model could be improved by taking into account seasonal
563 migrations, non-farming activities, and cash crops that are (1) not destined at the urban popu-
564 lations consumption, and (2) that provide an income to the rural population, thus diminishing
565 their demand for subsistence crops. Additionally, to predict the evolution of land-uses in the
566 region, additional data needs to be considered to understand how fuelwood is replaced to satisfy
567 energetic needs.

568 Other simplifying hypotheses were used in our model. For example, wood productivity,
569 accounted through the constant $fuel_wood_{prod}$, is known to depend on rainfall, though there is

570 no simple equation linking one to the other [Brandt et al., 2019]. Similarly, the consumption
571 of cereal, cer_{conso} , was considered a constant without taking into account possible variations
572 since the 1960s. However, the prevalence of undernourishment varied considerably during
573 our period of analysis, with levels decreasing from 31.5% between 1997 and 1999 to 10%
574 between 2014 and 2016 [Toure, 2019]. As a consequence, the demand for cereals, and thus
575 for croplands, is expected to be lower than predicted in our model in the beginning and to
576 rise across the years with the decrease in undernourishment prevalence. Taking into account
577 undernourishment could thus lead the switch to intensification to occur later. In addition, we
578 neglected spatial effects and in particular the fragmentation of landscapes. As a consequence,
579 crop residues are always considered available for livestock fodder even though most pastoralism
580 practices are localized at the centre north of Senegal, and thus sometimes very far away from
581 croplands [Bakary et al., 2019]. Finally, the entirety of Senegals lands are considered available
582 for farmers to use. However, a large part of the territory doesnt benefit directly to the population
583 because of large-scale land acquisitions in the agricultural sector, Sub-Saharan Africa being the
584 worlds most targeted area for land investments [Interdonato et al., 2020][Bourgoin et al., 2023].
585 In 2016, just accounting for foreign investors, 3% of arable lands were declared under contract
586 [Harding et al., 2016]. Consequently, our results are to be interpreted with consideration for
587 simplifying hypotheses and the exclusion of certain factors of influence.

588 Finally, a main limitation of our model comes from the difficulty to find high quality exoge-
589 nous time-series. Consequently, uncertainties could only be taken into account for the national
590 rangeland productivity. In addition, in some cases, data is lacking (e.g. regional livestock time-
591 series). In others, it is collected through surveys. Although this method is a powerful tool
592 to collect data and to make population level inferences [Couper, 2017], in Senegal, less than
593 10% of households declare their agricultural activity, making this field predominantly informal
594 [DAPSA, 2021]. With no high accuracy historical time-series accessible, agricultural data thus
595 mainly comes from estimations.

596 **5 Perspectives**

597 With the sensitivity analysis of section 3.1, parameters which uncertainty increase the more the
598 model output variance have been identified. Further research on these parameters would thus
599 contribute to diminishing model output uncertainty.

600 This model could be refined through the addition of different components. In Senegal,
601 due to the disappearance of fallow lands associated with insufficient manure, and no economic
602 possibility to compensate through the use of intrants, land degradation started occurring, in
603 particular since the end of the Senegalese agricultural program in the 1980s. One such form of
604 land degradation in the Sahel is wind erosion, with lands presenting no plant life, root structures
605 nor organic matter [Niane-Badiane and Szempruch, 1998]. Degraded lands cannot be used for
606 agriculture without time or costly interventions to rebuild soil fertility, they thus represent a
607 land category different from the unused areas of our model. Since our model predicts the

608 pressure on cultivated land through the crop fallow cycle, it would be interesting to integrate the
609 economic capacity of farmers to compensate nutrient loss through manure and intrans. This
610 module would predict the magnitude of land degradation and allow us to assess the impact of
611 degradation on the evolution of land-uses.

612 Economic driving forces were implemented by Rasmussen et al. (2012) in their model of
613 Sahelian land-use change developed on Burkina Faso [Rasmussen et al., 2012]. They included
614 factors such as crop prices, outmigration, and available labour forces. Considering the impact of
615 non-farming activities on agriculture in the Groundnut basin dynamics, implementing a similar
616 economic module would be relevant in our model but requires a precise analysis and quantifi-
617 cation of migratory fluxes and economic dynamics in Senegal. For example, remittances, that
618 is to say the money sent by work migrants to their home community, facilitate the reconversion
619 of rural populations to non-agricultural activities, leading to a decrease in the pressure for land.
620 Conversely, remittances are associated with higher investment in mechanization and agricul-
621 tural intensification, leading to increased yields [Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2011]. If data can be
622 acquired on outmigration from rural areas, it would thus be interesting to study their effects on
623 predicted land-uses in Senegal.

624 Finally, although modules could be added to refine model predictions, results at national
625 scale validated the use of this framework to reconstruct land-use dynamics nationally. The next
626 step with this model is to predict future land-uses. Through the application of Shared Socio-
627 Economic pathways (SSPs) and representative greenhouse concentration pathways (RCPs) to
628 the case of Senegal, representative evolutions of our exogenous variables could be generated
629 [Riahi et al., 2017]. Associated land-use predictions could thus be explored, and help identify
630 political leverages to reduce land-use conflicts and land degradation in the long term.

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634 **7 CRediT authorship contribution statement**

635 **Anem Dupr:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Methodology,
636 Resources, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing original draft . **Isabelle Gounand:**
637 Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing review & editing. **Paul-**
638 **Alain Raynal:** Formal analysis, Resources, Supervision. **Caroline Pierre:** Conceptualization,
639 Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing review & editing.

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9 Appendix: Between-model differences

This section presents the main differences between our model and SALU, the one from which it was adapted, developed in [Stéphenne and Lambin, 2001].

- **Use of available time-series rather than mechanistic assumptions:**

- **Cereal yield:** in SALU, the cereal yield is approximated as a linear function of rainfall. The economic capacity of farmers to compensate the decreasing following time then modulates this value with a degradation factor. In our study, the cereal yield is taken as input either from the reference database FAOSTAT [FAO, 2024] or from location-specific agronomic simulations [Brisson et al., 1998].

- **Rangeland productivity:** contrary to SALU, no explicit overgrazing was considered in our study. Rangeland productivity was rather estimated from climatic data at national scale, and from climatic and soil data with a Sahelian-specific grassland model for subnational scale [Mougin et al., 1995], thus implicitly accounting for factors affecting soil fertility.

- **Sensitivity analysis:** no parameter uncertainty was taken into account in SALU. In particular, the crop/past ratio parameter is set to $\frac{2}{3}$, whereas we explore the full range of possible parameter values based on currently available data.

- **Reproducibility:** implementation was made on Stella for SALU, without a released version with calculation steps. Our model was implemented in Python and made accessible online [Dupré, 2024].

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Table(Editable version)

Parameter	Description	Unit	Value in SALU	Literature range	Sources	Conditions
<i>biom_{conso/expansive}</i>	Livestock forage consumption under expansive agriculture	tonnes/eq. TLU/year	4.6	[3.4, 6.1]	1: Le Hourou and Hoste (1977) 2: Behnke and Scoones (1993) 3: Leeuw and Tothill (1990)	1: African Sahelo-Sudanian zone, 1977 2: African savannahs, 1983 3: Sub-Saharan Africa, 1993
<i>biom_{conso/intensive}</i>	Livestock forage consumption under intensive agriculture	tonnes/eq. TLU/year	2.3	[1.7, 3.0]	1: Le Hourou and Hoste (1977) 2: Behnke and Scoones, (1993) 3: Leeuw and Tothill (1990)	1: African Sahelo-Sudanian zone, 1977 2: African savannahs, 1983 3: Sub-Saharan Africa, 1993
<i>cer_{conso}</i>	Consumption of cereals of the Senegalese population	kg/inhab/year	360	[109.8, 327.1]	1: Bricas et al. (2013) 2: FAOSTAT analytical brief (2023) 3: Honfoga and van den Boom (2003) 4: Lipinski et al. (2013) 5: FoodData Central (2019)	1: Mean on Abidjan, Bamako, Bissau, Cotonou, Dakar, Lom, Niamey and Ouagadougou, 2008. 2: Africa, 2010 - 2021 3: Sahelian countries, 1961 - 2000 4: Global, 2011 5: Global, 2019
<i>cult_freq</i>	Cultivation frequency driving the crop-fallow cycle	year	2	[1, 3]	Bonetti and Jouve (1999)	Sub-Saharan Africa, 1999
<i>fuel_wood_{conso/rur}</i>	Fuel wood needs : rural consumption	m ³ /inhab/year	0.65	[0.41, 1.26]	Ki-Zerbo (1981)	Senegal, 1981
<i>fuel_wood_{conso/urb}</i>	Fuel wood needs : urban consumption	m ³ /inhab/year	0.85	[0.41, 1.26]	Ki-Zerbo (1981)	Senegal, 1981
<i>fuel_wood_{prod}</i>	Fuelwood productivity of natural vegetation	m ³ /year/ha	0.75	[0.1, 3.0]	Picard et al. (2006)	Dry savannahs in Africa
<i>a_{biom_prod}</i>	Slope of <i>biom_{prod}</i>	Tonnes/ha/m	0.00375	[0.0025, 0.005]	Breman and De Wit (1983)	Central Mali, 1976 - 1981
<i>b_{biom_prod}</i>	Intercept of <i>biom_{prod}</i>	Tonnes/ha	0.15	[-0.20, 0.30]	Breman and De Wit (1983)	Central Mali, 1976 - 1981
<i>crop_past_ratio</i>	Crop/pasture trade-off coefficient	None	0.4	[0, 1]		